

Laser induced excited state properties of 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cyclohepten-5-ol

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A number of photophysical properties of 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cyclohepten-5-ol have been measured for the first time including the emission, fluorescence and phosphorescence, and triplet-triplet absorption spectra. Decay parameters for the triplet state of this molecule have also been measured in different conditions. The results are discussed and compared.

Relatively little is known concerning the photophysical properties of the molecule 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cyclohepten-5-ol, which corresponds, at least in its structure, to 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cyclohepten-5-one, 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cycloheptenes and the *cis*-isomer of stilbene. The literature reports studies on 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cyclohepten¹⁻⁴ and the crystal structure of its derivative 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cyclohepten-5-ol^{5,6}. This study of the title compound showed that the benzyl groups accept hydrogen bonds from a hydroxy and an ethynyl group, one to each face of the ring.

For both the hydrogen bonds, energies around $-1.3 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ have been calculated. The bond donated by the hydroxy group has unusual geometry and is directed almost linearly at a C atom with $\text{H}\cdots\text{C} = 2.36 \text{ \AA}$. The title compound was prepared starting from 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cyclohepten-5-one. All operations were performed in an atmosphere of dry argon using Schlenk and vacuum techniques. Solvents were dried by standard methods and distilled prior to use. Nmr and ir spectra are recorded and crystallographic data were analysed⁵⁻⁷. The work reported here was undertaken with the aim of determining the values of a number of photophysical parameters which are of significance to the photochemistry of the excited singlet and triplet states.

Results and Discussion

The one-photon absorption and emission spectra, prompt fluorescence and P-type delayed fluorescence decays, triplet-triplet absorption spectrum and triplet decays in different condition are reported. The identity of the delayed fluorescence and prompt fluorescence spectra excludes the possibility of the triplet state spectra observed due to an impurity with a low-lying triplet state. Fig. 1 shows the one-photon absorption and prompt fluorescence spectra of 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cyclohepten-5-ol in cyclohexane at room temperature. The peaks in Fig. 1 correspond to $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ and $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transitions. The shape of the fluorescence spectrum is similar to that of 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cycloheptene emission band at 320–480 nm⁴. Fig. 2 shows uncorrected and corrected fluorescence spectra of the title compound in cyclohexane at room temperature; recording conditions being

Fig. 1. The one-photon absorption and prompt fluorescence spectra of 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cyclohepten-5-ol in cyclohexane at room temperature.

Fig. 2. The corrected and uncorrected prompt fluorescence spectra of 5H-dibenzo[a,d]cyclohepten-5-ol in cyclohexane at room temperature : (1) corrected for a view phototube response and (2) uncorrected spectrum, $\lambda_{ex} = 300$ nm.

excited 2 nm bandpass, view : 4 nm bandpass, 1 s counting time per step. The peak of the corrected spectrum is blue-shifted by about 5 nm, but the shape of the emission is not changed. Figs. 3 and 4 show prompt and P-type of delayed fluorescence emissions. Decay times were determined to be 12 ± 1 and 46 ± 1 ns for prompt and P-type delayed

Fig. 3. The prompt fluorescence decay of 5H-dibenzo[a,d]cyclohepten-5-ol in cyclohexane at room temperature.

Fig. 4. P-type delayed fluorescence decay of 5H-dibenzo[a,d]cyclohepten-5-ol in cyclohexane at room temperature.

fluorescences respectively. The shape of the fluorescence emission spectrum will be independent of the wavelength used to excite it because emission always takes places from the level S_1 , independent of the molecule that is originally excited. Secondly, the shape of the fluorescence emission spectrum will generally be similar to the shape of the first absorption band. Because the distribution of levels in the first excited state which is responsible for the shape of the first absorption band, is generally similar to the distribution of the levels in the ground state, and is responsible for the shape of fluorescence band.

All types of delayed fluorescences involve a metastable state, which is first converted to an excited singlet state before emitting. P-type of delayed fluorescence is produced by triplet-triplet annihilation, and its decay time depends on the lifetime of T_1 state. The efficiency of P-type (pyrene-type) delayed fluorescence is proportional to the rate of absorption of exciting light,

$h\nu =$ P-type of delayed fluorescence, rate $k_q = [T_1]^2$, where, k_q is the rate of quenching. The other types of delayed fluorescences were tested but unfortunately due to the very low emission signals none of them were detectable. Fig. 5 shows the triplet decay at 425 nm and the decay time was determined to be 174 ± 1 ns in the presence of air. Figs. 6 and 7 show triplet-triplet absorption and phosphorescence spectra ($\lambda_{ex} = 280$ nm) of the title compound in cyclohexane at room temperature. Triplet-state is stable, therefore it was possible to record phosphorescence spectrum at liquid nitrogen temperature. The spectrum is structured and the

Fig. 5. The triplet decay of 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cyclohepten-5-ol in cyclohexane at room temperature.

Fig. 6. Triplet-triplet absorption spectrum of 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cyclohepten-5-ol in cyclohexane at room temperature.

origin is easily identified as the 415 nm. The spectrum of Fig. 6 agrees partially with that determined for 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cycloheptene in solution⁴. Quenching of excited singlet states by inorganic anions is known to produce triplet states with unit efficiency in many cases⁸. This can be used to determine the efficiency of the intersystem crossing process which produces the triplet in the unquenched molecule⁹.

While it is clear that care must be exercised in applying the results presented here to 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cycloheptene, the idea of using structurally similar molecules to obtain information about molecules which are inaccessible to direct measurement appears to hold promise. It has been suggested¹⁰, on theoretical grounds, that the success of this method is due not only to its formal similarity to 5*H*-

Fig. 7. Phosphorescence spectrum of 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cyclohepten-5-ol in cyclohexane at 77 K.

dibenzo[*a,d*]cycloheptene, but also to the similarity in conformation of the two molecules. Similar studies using as an analogue may have wide application as a method of analysing photochemical reactions.

Oxygen quenches the triplet states of organic molecules because the ground state of oxygen is in the triplet-state, and the energy of the triplet oxygen is close to the energy values of the triplet states of the most organic molecules. In the presence of oxygen, most of the triplet states of organic molecules are quenched. Therefore, the decay time of P-type delayed fluorescence of the title compounds will be decreased. This is true for all kinds of delayed fluorescences : P-type (pyrene-type), E-type (eosin-type), and B-type (Bayrakçeken type), except R-type (recombination type)¹¹.

Experimental

5*H*-Dibenzo[*a,d*]cyclohepten-5-ol (Aldrich) was used as received. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade. 5*H*-Dibenzo[*a,d*]cyclohepten-5-ol solutions (2×10^{-5} M) were made in cyclohexane, ethanol, methanol and benzene at room temperature; the solvents purity was 99.9%. Absorption spectra were recorded using a Cary-219 spectrophotometer and the emission spectra using a Perkin-Elmer MPF-2A spectrophotometer. The singlet and triplet transient phenomena were excited with a laser flash photolysis set-up consisting of a Q-switched and mode-locked Nd : YAG laser system and dye laser system. A kinetic absorption spectrophotometer with nanosecond response (Baush & Lomb), uv-visible high intensity monochromator and RCA 4840 photomultiplier were used. A Tektronix 7912 digitizer and LSI-11 microprocessor unit were used to control the experiments and processed the data at the initial stage. The data from LSI-11 were finally transferred to a time-shared PDP 11/55 computer system for storage and further analysis. The flash photolysis experiments were car-

ried out in different conditions. Quartz cells ($1 \times 0.2 \text{ cm}^2$) were used with the absorbed light passing along the 0.2 cm path-length. The exciting laser beam intersected the cell at angles in the range $20\text{--}90^\circ$, and the flash duration time was $3.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ ns}$.

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